

INNOVATIVE MINI 3-AXIS COMPUTER NUMERICAL CONTROL (CNC) MACHINE FOR THE FABRICATION OF PRINTED CIRCUIT BOARDS (PCBS)

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ABSTRACT

In the manufacturing industry of Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs), the quality and reliability of circuits are highly dependent on the accuracy of the manufacturing processes. In this work, all the effects of inaccuracies in etching during the manufacturing process and the causes of malfunction in PCB circuits are investigated and resolved via a Computer Numerical Control (CNC) device. The mechanics behind a PCB milling machine design and construction have been investigated to identify the roots and fundamental techniques in CNC milling technology. To advance innovation in this project, the machine control and command processes as well as the positioning information were forwarded from the controlling software via a serial port connection directly to the milling machine's on-board controller, which in turn controlled the motion and continuous monitoring of the various components that moved the milling head and controlled the spindle speed at speeds ranging from 30,000 to 100,000 RMP. Typically, this drive system comprises nonmonitored stepper motors for X-Y, an on-off nonmonitored solenoid, a pneumatic piston or lead screw for the Z-axis, and a DC motor control circuit for spindle speed, none of which provide positional feedback.

This study incorporated both milling and laser etching capabilities into a single CNC machine for PCB milling.

Keywords: Computer Numerical Control, Fabrication, Milling, Electric Motors, STEM

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1. INTRODUCTION

Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs) are integral components in all electronic equipment, and their ability to transfer wearable devices to satellite devices, airplanes and medical devices is paramount (printedcircuits.com, 2023). Failures in PCB functionality occur for several reasons, and if not corrected, they could result in total disfunction or improper functioning of the PCB. The complexity of PCB designs and manufacturing processes increases the likelihood of PCB malfunction due to failure issues. Thus, it is crucial to take appropriate action in cases of failure (kingsunpcb.com, 2024).

Congruently, mistakes in design, including inadequate clearances or inaccurate measurements, can contribute to some of these failures and could have adverse effects on device operation. Some could be disastrous and mostly emanate from manufacturing process issues such as over etching or incorrect drilling (Samir M. 2022). PCB milling is an alternate process in PCB fabrication; it is conducted by etching sections of copper from a PCB sheet to replicate the signal traces, pads, and structures in accordance with designs from a layout file and is a type of digital circuit board (DCB) plan. Like the prevalent and well-known chemical PCB etching process, the subtractive PCB milling technique is carried out primarily with a Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machine. Unlike the chemical etching process, PCB milling is usually a nonchemical procedure, allowing it to be carried out in a laboratory or office setting without exposing workers to dangerous chemicals (pcbastore. (2021). The performance of the system, milling accuracy and control, state (sharpness, temper) of the milling bits, and individual feed/rotational speeds play major roles in determining the quality of a PCB milled circuit board. In contrast, the state of the etching chemicals and the precision and/or caliber of the mask used to shield the copper from the chemicals determine the quality of a circuit board during the chemical etching process (Khamroev K. et al. 2023). The key advantages of PCB milling make it vital for both the prototyping and manufacturing of electronic devices. This includes the fact that one does not have to use chemicals to produce PCBs, which makes it user friendly for teaching and demonstration purposes. In general, the outsourcing of any type of prototype takes the same form as is true for PCB boards. As an alternative, employing the wet technique to create PCBs internally raises issues with chemical disposal (Handel L. and Strazdus S. 2021).

Thus, it is difficult to create high-resolution boards with the wet process, and even when created, the PCB must still be drilled and ultimately cut out of the substrate material.

Nevertheless, CNC machine fabrication eliminates the need for wet processing and provides a quick turnaround time for the production of boards. If drilling is already performed on a CNC machine, then the same machine would be needed for milling and drilling. Drilling, cutting and milling are performed via a CNC machine.

Even basic boards that are easy to mill would be very challenging to process in a laboratory setting by wet etching and then manual drilling without the use of state-of-the-art equipment, which is typically more expensive than CNC milling machines. Nevertheless, milling is not expected to replace etching in large manufacturing, even though drilling boards with a CNC is currently a common procedure.

1.1. Research Problem

STEM education is enhanced with the introduction of hands-on practical sessions to practicalize and demonstrate theoretical lessons learned. The inaccuracies of the processes adopted by most applied manufacturing technologies are the main reasons for electronic circuit malfunction. Therefore, an alternative process to resolve some of the inaccuracies that cause major factors affecting the manufacturing process and the corresponding effects on the level of malfunctioning of circuits is necessary to identify the merits of the application of CNCs, which can contribute to improving the research and fabrication ability of engineering students. The study of manufacturing inaccuracies and their effects on circuits is very important, as it paves the way for making processes more accurate and building robust PCB circuits to meet customer or user satisfaction.

Thus, there is a need to promote enhanced fabrication techniques in the manufacturing of PCBs by applying innovation and technology to provide a means of designing and constructing PCBs at the university and to promote innovative alternatives to antique processes, utilizing digital electronic applications to solve today's challenging problems as well as to widen the scope of applications of digital electronics.

1.2. Research Objective

The objective of this study is to design an innovative mini-3-axis CNC machine for the fabrication of printed circuit boards (PCBSs).

The specific objectives are as follows:

- To incorporate the milling and laser drilling system into the CNC machine.
- To simulate and generate schematics for PCB fabrication
- To produce PCBs via the CNC machine

2. OVERVIEW OF CIRCUIT BOARD MILLING

Since the "plotting head" of a circuit board mill can move in the X–Y plane and be lifted or pulled down, it functions similarly to a three-axis plotter. As a mill, the "plotting head" is essentially a high-speed motor that has a drill or router bit attached to it. A router bit is utilized to create copper traces. The router is moved in the X–Y plane after being pressed down onto the copper-clad board surface.

The router creates an isolation channel by removing copper as it travels. When two isolation channels are machined on either side, a copper trace is formed or, more accurately, left behind (Kannan Megalingam R. (2018)).

A drill bit is used in place of the router bit to produce the holes on the circuit board. After the drill bit is positioned at the desired X-Y location with the milling head up, the head is momentarily pressed down and then released. Different drill bit sizes are employed on the basis of the circuit board's requirements (Kannan Megalingam R. (2018)).

2.1. The PCB Milling Process

To create routes and signal traces on the basis of the layout design, PCB milling is the process of removing unnecessary copper from a circuit board. The milling process typically takes half an hour. Nevertheless, a few factors could influence the procedure. The bit thickness, circuit board dimensions, and components that are available are a few of these variables. The quality of the board determines how accurate and sharp the milling bits are.

Vectors and rasters are the two main categories of milling software. While Vector relies on data given by Raster, Raster has a lower operating resolution. The PCB milling process involves two systems: software and hardware systems. Therefore, the interaction of the user and the hardware through the software allows for circuit board formation (Kannan Megalingam R. (2018)).

- **Software system** – The software is divided into two categories: vectors and raster. The software program is used to choose the preferred milling speed. The milling speed can be regulated by the stepper motor because the leadscrew and milling head are synchronized.
- **Hardware system** – The hardware system is a numerically controlled milling machine. It may have either a serial or a port that connects to the main control.

i. X/Y axes control

To match the movements of the two assemblies, the milling head and leadscrew are connected in turn. For the X/Y axes.

ii. Z-axis control

There are various methods for achieving movement along the z-axis. A solenoid, a pneumatic cylinder, or a precise stepper motor can start motion. With a Z-axis drive, the most common control mechanism is a solenoid pressing against a spring.

The milling head is pressed down by the solenoid when it is powered. The z-axis can also move with the aid of a pneumatic cylinder that is connected to a gate valve and is controlled by software. The cylinder is not very large. Limiting the range as a result (NASA, 2020).

In this case, a stepper motor is better than the other two approaches in terms of precision requirements. The milling head is moved by this technology in tiny, calculable stages. The program regulates the stepper motor, giving the user control over speed. The speed limiter achieves:

- Application of the user's selected number of steps
- Preventing hammering by smooth development of the bits toward the board

There is often one major challenge associated with PCB milling: achieving a uniform milling depth. This can be addressed by levelling; PCB milling offers a cost-effective solution to make strong boards.

3. METHODOLOGY

The project structure is broken down into various component parts and subsystems, showing their interrelationship in the development of our device. The workflow process for this chapter is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Workflow diagram of the design

PCB milling via a CNC machine yields a higher resolution output and can handle more complex circuits. It can also automate the process of drilling holes, hence saving the designer time during prototyping.

3.1. Production Design Specifications (PDS)

A rigid structure of a PCB milling machine will yield an optimum output. The rigid structure reduces vibrations and results in finer outputs. The design chosen in this process aims to reduce vibrations to a minimum. This machine is made of several materials, such as metals, plastics, wood and some electrical and electronic components (Costin S. and Dragomirescu C. (2013).

In this case, a few preliminary design draughts or sketches created via the AutoCAD program were used to select the final design. Determining the necessary criterion, which is first the length of travel, was the next step. The X, Y, and Z axes' total length of travel between two points is known as the length of the trip. The Z, Y, and X axes all move up and down, left and right, and front and back, respectively. The X-, Y-, and Z-axis travel lengths that need to be designed are 10 cm each. This construction consists of cut papers, engrave leather, wood, plastic cards, and slices of metal sheets or blocks. Because it requires fewer resources, it is incredibly inexpensive to build.

3.1.1. Design Conceptualization

Five concept designs of the mini-CNC machine are proposed, as shown in Figures 2 - 6.

Design Concept 1

Table 1 Advantages and disadvantages of design Concept 1

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to design and fabricate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly • High cost to manufacture • Heavy weight • Not safe

Figure 2 Stepper motors and spindle motors 1

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Design Concept 1, shown in Figure 2, consists of 3 stepper motors and one spindle motor. The advantages and disadvantages of this design concept are tabulated in Table 1.

Design Concept 2

Table 2 Advantages and disadvantages of design Concept

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aesthetically pleasing design • Can be used continuously • Simple yet effective design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly • High cost to manufacture • Not safe in operation • Rare parts in local market

Figure 3 Stepper Motors and Spindle Motor 2

Design Concept 2 is shown in Figure 3. This concept seems to be a good design, but the frame seems to be weak, as illustrated in Table 2.

Design Concept 3 Concept

Table 3 Advantages and Disadvantages of the Design

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aesthetical design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly • High cost to manufacture • Not safe in operation • Rare parts in local market

Figure 4 Stepper motors and Spindle Motor 3

Design Concept 3, shown in Figure 4, looks stylish and has a rigid frame that can be made of wood and aluminum. The advantages and disadvantages of this design concept are tabulated in Table 3.

Design Concept 4

Table 4. Advantages and disadvantages of design concept 4.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple and aesthetical design • Easy to manufacture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly • High cost to manufacture • Not safe in operation • Rare parts in local market

Figure 5 Stepper Motors and Spindle Motor 4

Design Concept 4, shown in Figure 5, has a rigid frame and a good design. However, this design is very costly to manufacture and requires many materials. The advantages and disadvantages of this design concept are tabulated in Table 4.

Design Concept 5

Table 5 Advantages and disadvantages of design Concept 5

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aesthetical design • Easy to manufacturing • Most parts are available in the markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require more workshop skills

Figure 6 Stepper motors and Spindle motor 5

Design Concept 5, as shown in Figure 6, has a compact and good design. This design seems to be cost-effective to manufacture and requires simpler materials. The advantages and disadvantages of this design concept are tabulated in Table 5.

Table 6 Concept design criteria for the proposed five design concepts

No	Criteria	Weights (%)	Design concepts				
			1	2	3	4	5
1	Ease to use	10+		+	+	+	+
2	Simplicity	10-		+	+	-	+
3	Complexity	10+		-	-	-	+
4	Safety	20-		-	-	-	+
5	Weight	50+		+	+	-	+
6	Low cost			-	+	-	-
7	Wow			+	-	+	+
Total			+4	3	4	2	6
Total -			3	4	3	4	1
overall score			1	-1	1	-2	5
Weighted overall score			10-10		10-20		50

The Pugh matrix is used to evaluate the five proposed design concepts. The Pugh matrix allows designers to compare a number of design concepts, ultimately leading to the best-suited criteria. One of the main advantages of using the Pugh matrix is that it can handle many decision criteria. The design concept criteria can be found in Table 6.

Table 6 shows that Design Concept 5, shown in Figure 6, has the highest overall score. Thus, it will be chosen as the final design concept of the mini-CNC milling machine of this project. The frame of the CNC machine uses plywood, stainless steel and aluminum alloy.

3.2.1. Design Analysis

SOLIDWORKS® 2017 software was used to produce the solid models of the CNC machine. The isometric, front, side and top views of the main parts of the CNC machine are shown in Figure 7, and the solid casing of the CNC machine is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7 a) Isometric view; b) Front view; c) Side view; d) Top view

3.3. Material Selection

The main tools used in mechanical design include wood boards, aluminum and aluminum plates, handles, mounts, stepper motors, ball bearings, leadscrews and nuts, and shafts. These are the main components that constitute the mechanical aspect of the machine.

Table 7 List of Materials of the Prototype

ITEM NO	PART NAME	QTY
1	Wood frame size 20 cm by 6 cm	4
2	Big stainless steel Rods size 42 cm	2
4	Joints	3
5	Small lead screw size 36 cm and 13 cm	2
6	Stainless steel pillow block bearing Bolt	12
8	Aluminium plate	1
9	Aluminium: 40 cm by 2 cm	4
11	Stainless Steel Socket Countersunk Screws	80
13	Side plates (wood)	2
15	Stainless steel shaft size 36 cm and 12 cm	5
17	Handle spindle	1
19	Stepper motor	3
20	8 mm Calibre Standard Linear Bearings	2
21	Spindle Mount	1
22	Spindle motor	1
23	Power supply	1
24	3 Axes CNC Driver	1

3.3.1. Motor Selection

Conducting motor selection first is encouraged because it has a direct bearing on both the driving mechanism and the control system. Steppers, servos, and two distinct motors were utilized. The motors that rotate are called stepper and servo motors.

All of these methods are suitable for undertaking this project because each has distinct strengths and shortcomings. In motors with rotary motion, converting rotary motion into linear motion always requires the use of a lead screw.

Table 8 Motor differences between Stepper and Servo

	Stepper	Servo
Price	Low	High
Control	Generally open loop	Close loop
Resolution	Determine by step/rev	Determine by encoder
Dynamic behavior	Low speed	High speed allowed
Accuracy	Low if using micro stepping	High

Currently, steppers are the most reasonably priced actuation option for machine tools. Stepper motors are used to drive the axes in several commercially available tiny CNC machines, such as CNC Baron and TORMACH, and an encoder is used to indicate the current position. The encoder serves only as an assessment tool for modest position offset adjustments, and the control remains open loop.

3.3 2. Linear Guides and Lead Screw Selection

The rolling-bearing slides are the least expensive option out of the three slides that were taken into consideration. It has an infinite range of motion, is lightweight, and is small. It is, nevertheless, the least rigid and has the most friction. The cross-roller guides also have a restricted range of motion, but they have the same amount of friction as recirculating ball slides and the maximum stiffness and robustness out of the three slides. The cross-roller guide is the greatest option since it only requires a small amount of travel for this project and because it can work at a significantly greater bandwidth owing to its increased stiffness.

3.4. Construction of the Prototype

The frame of the CNC milling cutting and laser cutting machine has a linear moment and driving systems as follows:

- Lead screws
- Linear ball bearings that provide free motion in a linear direction.
- A guide rod is used to guide the linear movement along the 3 axes of X, Y and Z.

3.4.1. Driving systems

The driving system consists of a motor driver, stepper motors, DC motors and a microcontroller board. The specifications of the motor driver, stepper motor and microcontroller board are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

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Figure 8 Motor driver circuit

Figure 9 DC motors and microcontroller board

In this project, the most common types of drivers are A4988 and DMOS, which are microstepping drivers with current and restate protection. has a 2A current and a maximum output capacity of 35 V. This is capable of operating stepper motors that are small to medium in size. A4899 drivers are currently available at a reasonable cost and 3.5A rate. The shield controller has manual or automatic control to limit and regulate torque as well as choose and regulate the start, stop, forward and reverse rotations. It guards against electrical faults and overloads.

The laser cutting, which is controlled by using a microcontroller board, is used to engrave the wood and paper. Figure 11 shows the laser cutting used in this project.

Figure 10 Laser Cutting Component

3.5. Electronic structure and software module

The schematic diagram in Figure 12 highlights the layout of the electronic components used in this project. The arrows show the connections between devices.

Figure 11 Schematic diagram of the electronic architecture of the proposed design of a CNC machine

The microprocessor, which is positioned top-left, is connected to three fundamental but crucial I/O devices: an LCD monitor for displaying and interacting with the Human-Computer Interface (HCI), a keyboard and a mouse for inputting data into the system.

The microcontroller and the stepper motor driver circuits for each of the axis motors are located on a (PCB) that is connected to the microcomputer. The connection is down via the 25-pin DB-25 parallel port.

The PCB and the Axis Motors that are controlled by it are powered by a power supply, which takes the 220-volt AC (RMS) power source's main electricity and transforms it into a 24-volt DC current. The abovementioned microcomputer provides one input to the PCB, which also receives power from a DC power source. The PCB then uses four wires, each in bipolar mode, to operate the two-axis stepper motors. Additionally, a relay switch that regulates the spindle motor's toggling is present on the PCB.

The powerful spindle motor is driven by a variable frequency drive (VFD) that is fueled by a second main power source. The spindle's RPM can be separately adjusted via a potentiometer knob on the VFD.

3.5.1. Software module

For more thorough PC-to-microcontroller backend processing, off-the-shelf software was employed, whereas open-source tools were utilized for the front-end human-computer interface (HCI).

Compatibility is guaranteed because both software programs need to interact with one another without any problems.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Knowledge in software engineering, electronics, and mechanics was required for this project. As per the project's goals, tests were carried out at different phases of the project's activity, and the outcomes of these tests were recorded. Here are a few key deliverables:

- An appropriate microcontroller-based configuration is created for managing machine operations.
- Evaluate how sensors are used and how their feedback affects system control and regulation.
- The right motors for every machine operation are chosen and acquired.
- Create or acquire a circuit for a motor driver.
- Create and build a voltage-regulating power supply, or buy and incorporate one.
- Provide an appropriate human-computer interface (HCI).
- Create an interpreter to translate machine language from G and M codes.

Importantly, the main goal of this project is to create a low-cost, straightforward CNC milling machine that can process softer metals while maintaining the design's extendibility. The design for manufacturability (DFM) principles were followed throughout the iterative design process. Once more, as Figure 13 illustrates, an open frame structure is used to construct the prototype CNC machine.

Fig 16a Top view

Fig 16b Isometric view

Fig 16 c Back view

Figure 13 Mechanical design and analysis 4.1 Mechanical Calculations

Torque And Theoretical Power Evaluation

The amount of torque needed for the axis motors to determine the cutting force values is calculated, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Machine torque evaluation

- The force exerted on the work piece is labeled F_c (cutting force) and is divided into its components F_{cx} , F_{cy} and F_{cz} .
- The work piece is rigidly mounted on the worktable, so there is no relative motion between them. Additionally, the values of the cutting forces are calculated via the following formula:

$$F = Ct^xw$$

Eqn. 1

F- principal cutting force in Newtons,

C - material constant at a given cutting speed and

rake angle, t- uncut chip thickness in mm,

w- width of cut in mm or length of the cutting edge in

engagement x- constant for material being machined.

x varies with the rake angle

The constant values were taken to be as follows since we decided that the work piece would be made of aluminum or lightweight steel.

$$C=500, t=0.15, x=0.70, w=20$$

$$\text{Hence, } F_{cx} = Ct^xw$$

$$F_{cx} = 500 \times 0.15^{0.70} \times 20, F_{cx} = 2650N, F_{cy} = F_{cx} \text{ and } F_{cz} = F_{cx} \tan(\beta)$$

$$F_{cz} = 2330 \times \tan(41.34) = 2330N$$

The total value of the force opposing the motion of the x-axis and y-axis motors is given by the following formula:

$$\text{Total load (L)} = F_{cx} + (F_{cz} + F_{cy} + W_t) \times \mu_s \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

Where;

W_t , the total load of the work piece, bed is taken to be 300N (30KG)

μ_s , the value of the coefficient of friction is assumed to be 0.3 Hence,

$$\text{Total Load (L)} = 2650 + (2330 + 2650 + 300) \times 0.3 \text{ Total}$$

$$\text{Load (L)} = 4234 \text{ N}$$

4.1.1 Calculating the Torque

The thread we use is the ACME square thread. The value of the total torque applied on the square thread by the load is given by the formula (Anon, 2011).

$$T_r = \frac{d_m}{2} \times \frac{L(\mu\pi d_m + l)}{(\pi d_m - \mu l)} + L\mu_c \frac{d_c}{2} \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

For the ACME square thread used,

$$\mu = 0.07, \text{ mean diameter } d_m = 9.525 \text{ mm, pitch } l = 2.1 \text{ mm}$$

Hence, this construction may be built with less material than the close frame structure, making it far more affordable to produce. The team decides to employ an open frame structure for this small-scale machine after weighing the advantages and disadvantages of both types of structures.

4.2. Computer Software for the CNC Machine

The G-Code directives that are serially received from the computer are necessary for this project. To read G-Code files, access the serial port, and deliver data serially to the microcontroller, a Java application was created. The software algorithm is shown in Figure 15.

Additionally, to adjust its parameters, an event listener is sent to the port to send a notification when data are received, and the function is executed by a separate thread to order and write the data on the serial port.

Similarly, the microcontroller used in this CNC project is **PIC18f4620**, which receives the G-Code commands and parse them; after parsing them, it executes each command and tells the machine to perform the task. Figure 16 shows the algorithm of the PIC software

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Figure 15 Software algorithm of the CNC machine

4.3 Testing and Validation

A test to determine if the machine stops at the same point of many cycles. A precision dial gauge was attached to the machine, and it was commanded to move one axis for a determined distance and then return. This cycle is repeated 15 times for each test

Figure 16 Microcontroller Software Algorithm for the CNC Machine

For every axis, the test is run ten times. The axis moved a total of 1500 mm, 3000 mm, and 6000 mm during these tests. Each time, the results fell between +0.01 mm and -0.01 mm. The attachment of the precision dial gauge to the machine for each axis test is depicted in Figure 17. At the conclusion of every test, Table 9 displays the measured offsets.

Figure 17 Precision Dial Gauge Test

Table 9 Measured offsets obtained from the repeatability tests

1500 mm test	Axis			3000 mm test				6000 mm test	Axis		
	X	Y	Z		X				X		Z
1	0,01	0,01	0,00	1	0,00	0,00	0,01	1	0,01	-0,01	0,00
2	0,01	0,00	0,00	2	0,00	-0,01	-0,01	2	0,00	0,00	0,00
3	-0,01	0,01	0,00	3	0,01	-0,01	-0,01	3	0,00	0,01	0,01
4	0,01	-0,01	0,00	4	0,01	0,00	0,01	4	0,01	-0,01	0,00
5	0,00	-0,01	-0,01	5	0,00	-0,01	-0,01	5	-0,01	-0,01	0,01
6	0,01	-0,01	-0,01	6	-0,01	0,00	-0,01	6	0,01	-0,01	0,00
7	-0,01	0,01	0,01	7	-0,01	0,01	0,00	7	0,01	0,00	0,00
8	0,01	0,00	0,01	8	0,00	0,00	-0,01	8	0,00	0,00	0,00
9	0,00	0,01	0,00	9	0,01	-0,01	0,01	9	0,00	0,00	0,01
10	0,01	0,00	0,01	10	0,01	-0,01	0,00	10	0,00	0,01	-0,01

PCB tracks can have thicknesses of as little as 0.1 mm. Such tracks must be able to be made by the machine. To verify this. To test the machine's ability to create thin tracks, a PCB was filled with several tracks. The PCBs are measured in Figure 18. The machining diameter fluctuates along the depth of the machining due to the V-shaped tool. If the PCB was completely plain, which it was not, this would not be an enormous concern. The machining diameter varies by 0.35 mm for every 0.01 mm of depth, varying the amount of material removed and influencing the thickness of the tracks.

The thickness of the sample tracks used in this test ranged from 0.1 to 1.00 mm. The measurements derived from the 0.1 mm samples are displayed in Table 10. Additionally, 0.89 mm less was the mean minimum thickness discovered than the minimum intended. However, the tool occasionally damaged the thinnest tracks because it could not line up exactly with the shaft. It is recommended that this machine have a minimum thickness of 0.1 mm because no broken tracks were observed throughout the tests.

Figure 18 Sample tracks measured with a profile projector

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After all these tests, several real PCBs were achieved, demonstrating how the machine performed on real cases. Figure 19 shows some of these PCBs.

Figure 19 PCBs constructed with the CNC milling machine

Finally, Figure 20 illustrates the setup of the laboratory-developed CNC machine with a laser cutting module.

Figure 20 Demo of the designed CNC machine at the GCTU laboratory

Table 10 Measured Thickness for the 0.1 mm Sample Tracks

Test 1—0,10 mm		Test 2 — 0,10 mm		Test 3 — 0,10 mm	
Track	Value	Track	Value	Trefik	Value
1	0,008	1	0,089	1	0,008
2	0,095	2	0,097	2	0,085
3	0,094	3	0,087	3	0,095
4	0,085	4	0,088	4	0,091
5	0,009	5	0,085	5	0,089
6	0,090	6	0,092	6	0,090
7	0,089	7	0,089	7	0,088
8	0,088	8	0,096	8	0,095
9	0,077	9	0,095	9	0,088
10	0,091	10	0,091	10	0,077

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

With the increasing demand for small-scale high-accuracy tools in different industries, the market for small-scale computer numerical control (CNC) machine tools has grown strongly, yet again, the use of small machine tools to manufacture small parts with high efficiency and flexibility in fabrication approaches while minimizing the capital cost has grown useful for small industries and business owners.

In this report, a mini-3-axis CNC milling machine incorporating a laser cutting device was designed. During the design stage, different common structure frames of the CNC milling machine were explored and analyzed. The most convenient structure frame (open frame vertical) of the CNC machine was used. The critical components of the CNC milling machine, such as the lead screw, guide line, stepper motor, DC motor and controller, were chosen on the basis of the research and target results. The best materials and components were chosen to accommodate hardness demands and budget constraints.

Most importantly, the CNC machine was fabricated and assembled in the GCTU electronics laboratory, and after completion, the machine was tested via three different techniques, i.e., circle testing, surface testing and small part adjustments, to ensure that the CNC machine works well and accurately.

Ultimately, a new design prototype was created and evaluated with features of calibration accuracy and ease of assembly to achieve the desired characteristics of a CNC machine with a comparably lower budget.

5.1. Recommendation

The design of a motion controller is crucial to engineering research, and for improvements in this area of study, there is a need to promote the development and construction of a motion controller to save money. To do this, the hardware must be self-constructed, and the connection must be developed as well. Moreover, the servo loop program, the interpolation program, and the HMI (human machine interface) must be written by the research team to improve teaching, learning, and STEM education.

Additionally, for this firmware to enable more user-friendly operations, an HMI is still lacking and needs to be developed. The best option is to use a touchscreen as the interface and a Raspberry Pi as the controller's "PC" terminal. As a result, the entire controller can be built into a box that is only a few square inches. With a USB drive, the user may effortlessly import machine code files into the Raspberry Pi, which comes with its own integrated Linux operating system. The Raspberry Pi may then effortlessly stream the machine code into Arduino via a different USB connector. Ultimately, the fabrication process should be optimized to achieve mass manufacturing in the future.

5.2. Limitations of the Study

This study is not without constraints. The limitations of this project are as follows:

- The machine cannot be operated remotely
- The parts are difficult to acquire
- The machine requires some amount of personal safety in operation.

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